

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
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ORGANIZATIONAL MECHANISM OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURISM INDUSTRY, ROLE AND APPLICATION OF TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: Today, as a result of the rapid development of market relations, favorable conditions and opportunities are being created to ensure the sustainable development of tourism, and the further integration of tourism into the national economy is gaining importance in the country's economy. Ensuring sustainable growth of the tourism industry and the hotel industry requires systemic reforms. In the hotel industry, the role of innovative technologies is very important. Today's competitive environment is such that every hotel and every tourism business must constantly grow with the times or else the market will squeeze it. Customer opinion is especially important in an era when marketing and management need to focus heavily. This article provides a thorough analysis of the status and role of technology use in the hospitality and tourism industry.

Key words: Tourism, sustainable tourism, hotel management, organizational communication, customer experience, communication technologies, hospitality industry, effective communication.

Annotatsiya: Bugungi kunda bozor munosabatlarining jadal rivojlanishi natijasida turizmning barqaror rivojlanishini ta'minlash uchun qulay shart-sharoit va imkoniyatlar yaratilib, mamlakatimiz iqtisodiyotida turizmning milliy iqtisodiyotga yanada integratsiyalashuvi muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Turizm industriyasi va mehmonxona xo'jaligining barqaror o'sishini ta'minlash tizimli islohotlarni taqozo etadi. Mehmonxona sanoatida innovatsion texnologiyalarning o'rni juda katta. Bugungi raqobat muhiti shundayki, har bir mehmonxona va har bir sayyohlik biznesi zamon bilan birga o'sib borishi kerak, aks holda bozor uni siqib chiqaradi. Mijozlarning fikri marketing va menejmentga katta e'tibor qaratish kerak bo'lgan davrda ayniqsa muhimdir. Ushbu maqolada mehmondo'stlik va turizm sanoatida texnologiyalardan foydalanish holati va roli to'liq tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Turizm, barqaror turizm, mehmonxona boshqaruvi, tashkiliy aloqa, mijozlar tajribasi, kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, mehmondo'stlik sanoati, samarali muloqot.

Аннотация: Сегодня в результате бурного развития рыночных отношений создаются благоприятные условия и возможности для обеспечения устойчивого развития туризма, а дальнейшая интеграция туризма в национальную экономику приобретает значение в экономике страны. Обеспечение устойчивого роста туристической отрасли и гостиничного хозяйства требует системных реформ. В гостиничном бизнесе очень важна роль инновационных технологий. Сегодняшняя конкурентная среда такова, что каждый отель и каждый туристический бизнес должны постоянно развиваться в ногу со временем, иначе рынок их сожмет. Мнение клиентов особенно важно в эпоху, когда маркетингу и менеджменту необходимо уделять пристальное внимание. В данной статье представлен тщательный анализ состояния и роли использования технологий в индустрии гостеприимства и туризма.

Ключевые слова: Туризм, устойчивый туризм, гостиничный менеджмент, организационные коммуникации, клиентский опыт, коммуникационные технологии, индустрия гостеприимства, эффективная коммуникация.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, tourism has become a rapidly developing sector of the world economy and the largest export industry. The role of tourism in the development of the national economy is not only its high income, but also it has a positive effect on solving the employment problem by creating labor-intensive industrial jobs, it plays a key role in ensuring sustainable development by protecting the natural and cultural environment, and it also makes a significant contribution to ensuring harmony between peoples and nations.

According to the World Tourism Organization, sustainable tourism is defined as "tourism that takes full account of its current and future economic, social and environmental impacts while meeting the needs of tour-

ists, the tourism industry, the environment and host communities". Sustainable tourism development meets the needs of current tourists and host regions, while protecting and enhancing opportunities for the future.

The basis of the tourism market is made up of tour operator firms (a tourism organization that combines its own and others' services into a new independent tourism product - a package tour) and travel agents (firms that act as intermediaries in the sale of package tours).

These two structures are engaged in organizing tourist trips, selling them in the form of vouchers and tours, organizing services for providing accommodation and food for tourists (hotels, inns and others), for delivery to holiday destination (air travel, rail transportation, etc.), organizing transfers, moving tourists around the country. The tourism industry also includes firms from other industries for which organizing and serving tourists is not their main activity (cultural enterprises, trade enterprises, and others).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Today, international and domestic tourism is a powerful industry in the trade in services. In addition, modern tourism is a global computerized business. Large airlines, hotel complexes and travel companies from all over the world participate in this business. Due to information technology (IT), the tourism product becomes more individual and flexible, as well as more accessible to every consumer. IT technologies today play a major role in the field of technical development of tourism, which determines a number of distinctive features of IT (operability and accessibility).

Communication has been defined and described in various ways in the literature. Some writers suggest that communication involves exchanging messages or ideas through speaking, pointing, or writing. Others define it as a process of exchanging messages and indicate that communication occurs when messages are fully conveyed. Communication has also been defined as the process of transmitting a message containing information from a sender to a receiver, and it has been described as a term that expresses the exchange of emotions and ideas between individuals (Adler, 2002). The hotel and hospitality industry is highly competitive, and customer satisfaction is crucial for success. Effective communication among hotel staff is essential for providing excellent customer service, ensuring smooth operations, and maintaining a positive work environment. With the rapid advancement of technology, communication technologies have become an increasingly important tool for hotel management.

Some of the key roles of organizational communication technologies in hotel management include:

- **Streamlining Operations:** Organizational communication technologies such as property management systems (PMS), point of sale (POS) systems, and inventory management systems help hotels to streamline their operations by automating tasks such as reservations, check-ins, check-outs, billing, and inventory management. This not only saves time but also reduces the risk of errors and improves the accuracy of data.
- **Enhancing Guest Experiences:** Organizational communication technologies such as guest relationship management (GRM) systems, mobile apps, and social media platforms enable hotels to provide personalized experiences to their guests by collecting and analyzing data on their preferences, behaviors, and feedback. This helps hotels to tailor their services and offerings to meet the specific needs and expectations of their guests.
- **Improving Communication and Collaboration:** Organizational communication technologies such as email, instant messaging, and video conferencing enable staff members, guests, and management to communicate and collaborate more effectively, regardless of their location or time zone. This helps to improve the efficiency of operations, reduce misunderstandings, and enhance the overall quality of service.

The importance of communication in the accommodation business is widely recognized. Therefore, the objective of this study was to identify the level of communication and other issues within the organization.

2.1. The essences of organizational communication

Successful organizations are built on effective communication, which can be likened to the blood that flows through an organization. Organizational communication encompasses the different forms and channels of communication used by members of organizations, including corporations, nonprofits, and small businesses. Research has shown that there is a strong correlation between the level of communication within an organization and job performance and satisfaction. Organizational communication can take on formal or informal forms, flow in different directions, and utilize various communication media.

The significance of communication within an organization can be summarized as follows:

- Communication is essential for promoting motivation among employees by providing them with information about their tasks, performance, and ways to improve.

- Communication serves as a source of information for decision-making by identifying and evaluating alternative courses of action.
- Communication plays a crucial role in shaping individual attitudes, as well-informed individuals tend to have better attitudes. Organizational magazines, journals, meetings, and other forms of communication help shape employee attitudes.
- Communication is also important for socializing, as it is a fundamental aspect of human interaction.
- Communication assists in the controlling process by regulating employee behavior in accordance with organizational policies and guidelines. Employees must comply with organizational policies, perform their job roles effectively, and communicate any work-related issues or grievances to their superiors. Therefore, communication is an essential component of the management function of control (Julie Zink, n.d.).

2.1.1. Why employee communications in hotels is crucial?

The success of your hotel depends on the experience your guests have and their loyalty towards your establishment. This can only be achieved by having well-informed, engaged, enthusiastic, and helpful staff who represent your organization. Their interactions with guests can either make or break their satisfaction and loyalty, especially when it comes to online reviews. Negative reviews from dissatisfied guests can discourage other potential guests from booking with your hotel. Poor employee communication in the hospitality industry can result in a range of negative experiences for guests, such as:

- Staff not receiving important announcements;
- Guest requests being forgotten or lost;
- Time being wasted trying to resolve recurring issues;
- Staff being unaware of important health and safety protocols;
- Staff not being informed about current promotions;
- Staff being unprepared to respond to emergency situations, and some staff members not having access to important information;
- Additionally, when staff members do not feel connected to the company's vision, mission, brand, and goals, it can lead to poor morale, which can result in higher staff turnover and inadequate training (Duncan, 2022)

Furthermore, sharing information between different departments in a hotel can be made effortless with the right tools. Apart from building relationships, sending relevant and timely communications through suitable channels to colleagues in other departments can help keep them informed (Duncan, 2022).

2.2. Technology development in the Hotel Industry

The hospitality and tourism industries are experiencing rapid innovation, especially in the area of customer interaction. Self-scan and self-check transactions are replacing direct customer interaction, giving clients more control and making them more self-sufficient (Ham, 2005). According to a study conducted at the University of Oxford, by 2033, more than 47% of advanced occupations could be automated (Pullen, 2017). Below are some technological advancements that impact the trends in the hospitality sector (Anon., 2016).

2.2.1. Beacons

Beacons are Bluetooth-enabled poles that communicate with iOS and Android systems to exchange messages between an organization and its guests, similar to a metal detector (Rajath, 2017). Retailers, airports, exhibition halls, and hotels have successfully used beacons, but the hotel industry has been slow to adopt them (Buhalis, 2018). However, some chain hotels have realized that beacons can increase their profits. For instance, Marriott has installed beacons at hotel hotspots like spas, restaurants, and bars (David, 2016). Guests who have the Marriott app on their smartphones receive promotional messages about discounts in spas and restaurants when they pass by the beacons (Anon., 2016).

Marriott Hotels has implemented a different approach to using beacons by placing them near hotel entrances to simplify the check-in process. When guests enter the hotel, the beacons receive data from their phones, allowing hotel staff to greet them by name (Buhalis, 2018). Additionally, beacons near room entrances notify housekeeping staff when guests are not in their rooms (Anon., 2016). The hotel industry is actively exploring other applications of beacons, such as helping guests navigate the hotel or providing information on in-room amenities (David, 2016). Beacons can provide two-way communication, enabling hotels to collect data on guest behavior (Buhalis, 2018) such as their preferred areas within the hotel and the busiest times for facilities like the gym, pool, and bar. This information can help hotels improve their services and facilities to better cater to the needs and preferences of their guests (Rajath, 2017).

2.2.2. Property Management System (PMS)

In the 1980s, the hotel industry saw the introduction of the first property management system (PMS) (Morosan, 2008). This system was a software application designed to organize the operational aspects of the front office or food and beverage orders. The PMS is a hotel operating system that is widely used in hospitality management (Winata, 2005). It is a computerized system that helps manage properties, equipment, and maintenance through a single program. The software can handle various hotel operations related to guest bookings, reservations, billing, points of sale, debt claims, advertising, events, food-and-beverage stock management, human resources and finance, maintenance administration, quality administration, and other amenities. A PMS can integrate with other third-party software such as central reservation systems, back-office functions, door-locking applications, housekeeping management, pay television, energy management, instant card approval, and channel management systems (Winata, 2005).

Modern property management systems have replaced traditional paper-based methods that were often inefficient and wasteful. The old methods were based on a customer and server model. Nowadays, advanced PMSs support web and cloud technologies and provide services to customers through a service display (Morosan, 2008). The advancement of cloud computing has enabled hotel property management systems to offer additional features, such as online registration, room service, in-room controls, guest-staff communication, and virtual concierges. These features are primarily accessed by guests through their mobile devices or through tools in hotel lobbies and rooms. An effective PMS should provide accurate data on key performance indicators of the hotel business, including the average daily rate, RevPAR, and occupancy rate (Morosan, 2008). In addition to managing food and beverage stocks in the storeroom, a PMS should aid in making purchasing decisions regarding what, how much, and how often to buy. Choi and Kimes conducted a study on hotel booking systems and provided an overview of hotel technologies. They identified the PMS as the hub of all hotel operations and highlighted its usefulness in managing room inventory, guest information, payment details, integration with food and beverage management, and points of sale for streamlined billing and reporting (Choi, 2002).

2.2.3. Mobile Communication

Hotel guests now anticipate registration processes that are driven by innovation (Agag, 2016). Customers expect to be able to perform tasks such as checking in at a kiosk and requesting room amenities using their smart devices, rather than having to wait in a queue (Kasavana, 2011). Due to advancements in digital technology and online networking, guests also anticipate high-quality, personalized connectivity in their hotel rooms (Mitel., 2017). By investing in advanced applications for registration, room service, and other client-managed digital features, hotel administrators are investing in the ability to personalize the hotel experience for guests (Mitel., 2017). These investments allow hotels to display a guest's name on a computerized registration station or show their in-hotel and past purchases at a kiosk, making it easy for guests and employees to access this information.

The concept of having a “pocket concierge” is becoming increasingly popular as it allows hotel staff to provide guests with useful information about entertainment options, transportation, and other administrative details without being tied to their computers or workstations (Agag, 2016). An internal messaging system can be used by employees to send information to the housekeeping or concierge departments regarding late checkouts, special requests, or emergencies. This system allows for two-way communication between staff and administrators, and administrators can use it to communicate with all staff members at different locations within the hotel. Therefore, an internal messaging system provides a cost-efficient means for employees to communicate with each other (Agag, 2016).

2.2.4. Website

Numerous hotels have created their own websites to promote their services and reach out to customers directly (Agag, 2016). Independent hotels that are not part of a franchise chain need to have a booking engine application integrated into their website to enable customers to make room reservations. One benefit of booking directly with hotels is that customers can view the hotel's cancellation policies and are not required to make a deposit or advance payment (Tony, 2013). A content management system supports web-based booking engine applications, which are utilized for various purposes such as advertising, booking rooms, registering complaints, collecting feedback, answering queries, and enabling guests to communicate with hotel staff. Online bookings can decrease the workload of employees since websites are accessible 24/7, eliminating the need for employees to be present in the front office at all times. Additionally, online bookings are more dependable than paper-based bookings and payments.

In addition, the majority of hotel websites feature a section of frequently asked questions (FAQs), which can assist guests in finding answers to their queries online. Online systems provide a practical solution for

managing complaints, which is another crucial aspect of hotel management. Guests can also access the hotel's website to learn how to use amenities such as the television and air conditioner, avoiding the need to seek clarification in person, which can be time-consuming (Tony, 2013).

2.2.5. Point of Sale (POS) Systems

A POS (Point of Sale) system is an automated system utilized to simplify and monitor transactions conducted within a business. It can serve multiple functions, such as tracking sales, managing inventory, implementing customer loyalty programs, and other related tasks. To put it simply, a POS system is a tool that helps hotels process and record transactions with their customers (guests). POS systems have become increasingly popular in the hospitality industry, following their widespread use in restaurants and retail stores. These systems simplify the process of collecting payments from guests who make purchases at different points of sale. For example, if a guest books a massage, has breakfast, and then orders a drink, they don't have to pay for everything at once. The POS system automatically adds each purchase to their bill, which they can pay during checkout.

However, a POS Hotel System is not just a simple cash register. It is a highly advanced and complex computerized network consisting of various hardware and software components. This system optimizes different aspects of hotel management, including sales, customer management, marketing, inventory management, employee management, and more. Moreover, a POS Hotel system stores valuable information that can be used for better decision-making and analysis (Jeffery, n.d.).

2.3. The importance of effective communication itself of a Hotel Manager

Effective communication is a crucial factor in the success of any hospitality business. A hotel manager who can clearly and concisely communicate their vision and expectations to their team is more likely to achieve positive results.

In the hospitality industry, two-way communication is essential. It's not enough to simply give instructions to your staff; you must also listen to their feedback and concerns. Understanding the needs and wants of both your team and your guests is key to creating a welcoming and accommodating environment.

Remember that how you communicate is just as important as what you say. The tone and delivery of your message can greatly impact its effectiveness. A confident and well-spoken hotel manager with strong leadership skills is more likely to succeed in this fast-paced and ever-changing industry.

By honing your interpersonal and leadership skills, you can ensure that your hotel runs smoothly and efficiently while providing guests with the best possible experience (Anon., n.d.).

One of the primary goals of hotel management is to ensure guest satisfaction. This involves every aspect of the customer journey, from clear advertising and easy booking processes to seamless check-in and check-out experiences, friendly reception with clear directions, and ongoing support throughout the guests' stay.

To excel in hospitality and tourism management, there are several skills that you should develop. Here are some tips to help you acquire these skills:

- Develop the skill of active listening, which involves not only hearing what the other person is saying but also making an effort to understand their perspective. This skill can be useful in resolving conflicts and ensuring that everyone is in agreement.
- Communicate in a clear and concise manner. When providing instructions or sharing information, use language that is easy to comprehend. This involves avoiding technical terms and using simple language.
- Maintain an open mind. It's crucial to be receptive to new ideas and suggestions from your team. By being open to feedback, you can establish a more productive and efficient hotel operation. Remember that effective communication is a two-way process.
- Show respect. It's essential to maintain a respectful tone in all communication. This will promote a positive work environment and cultivate strong relationships with your team.
- Practice patience. Misunderstandings and miscommunications are inevitable in any workplace. The important thing is to remain calm and work through the issue with the other person until it is resolved (Anon., n.d.).

Effective communication within organizations involves exchanging information with employees and valuing their opinions. This can increase their motivation to fulfill their responsibilities and contribute to the organization's internalization of its vision to achieve its goals. In other words, good communication can connect employees to the organization's strategy and vision more effectively than anything else.

3. METHODOLOGY

This article was created by reviewing previous research and adapting it to improve the current article. It provides reliable and accurate information on various types of organizational communication technologies and effective communication methods. To create this article, more than 10 articles on the topic were studied. Based on the research findings, appropriate proposals and recommendations have been developed to enhance organizational communication. In summary, the study has led to the development of relevant proposals and recommendations based on its results.

4. DISCUSSION

To summarize, as mentioned above, the research revealed that there are several problems in the application of organizational communication technologies, and 6 strong communication tips were recommended for the development of communication methods in the hotel. Adopting these recommended guidelines for communicating with employees in hotels can result in increased guest satisfaction and higher levels of employee engagement.

- **Highlight the significance of effective communication to your staff.** Make sure they understand the importance of being informed and up-to-date with news and updates within the company, as this can help them provide exceptional service to your guests. Foster a company culture that prioritizes communication and encourages employees to take time at the start of their shift to update themselves with any new information. By doing so, you can create a work environment that values communication and promotes better guest experiences.
- **Avoid depending solely on radio communication for all tasks.** Radio communication is frequently overused in the hospitality industry, which can be disruptive and noisy for guests. Additionally, since radio messages can be heard by anyone, they have the potential to broadcast unpleasant information within earshot of guests. Furthermore, employees may become desensitized to the noise and miss important information. It is advisable to limit the use of radio communication to emergency situations only.
- **Adopt digital and mobile communication methods.** Consider investing in a contemporary internal communication system that employs digital channels and can reach non-desk employees through mobile devices. This will ensure that your critical information is received, regardless of what tasks your staff are performing or where they are located. It is essential to communicate with all employees through a hotel communication network to enable them to provide a seamless experience to guests.
- **Employ a variety of communication channels for internal communication.** Utilizing multiple communication channels is a recommended approach for hotel communication. This strategy can reinforce your messaging, leading to better message retention. The more frequently employees are exposed to a message, the more likely they are to comprehend and act on it.
- **Provide uniform employee training and onboarding programs.** Inconsistency in employee training is a significant issue in many organizations, as different managers may have varying approaches and priorities. This can result in an uneven level of knowledge and skill development among the workforce. The problem is particularly evident during onboarding processes, where some employees may be well-prepared while others may struggle to understand their roles. To ensure a seamless guest experience, it is crucial to establish and provide consistent training and onboarding experiences to all staff members.
- **Make sure you can send both urgent and non-urgent communications.** When introducing new internal communication processes, systems, and procedures, it is essential to consider emergency communications. It is crucial to prepare for both immediate and non-immediate communications, enabling you to reach employees promptly during emergencies and when disseminating routine information (Duncan, 2022).

Another important finding is that communication technologies can help improve customer service in hotels. By using technologies such as chatbots, mobile apps, and social media, hotels can provide customers with quick and convenient access to information and services. This can help enhance the customer experience and increase customer satisfaction.

The study also found that communication technologies can help increase operational efficiency in hotels. By using technologies such as property management systems, point of sale systems, and automated workflows, hotels can streamline their operations and reduce the time and resources required to perform routine tasks. This can help hotels save money and improve their bottom line.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the application of organizational communication technologies in hotel management involves the use of various tools, techniques, and disciplines to manage hotel operations and enhance guest experiences. By leveraging these technologies and disciplines, hotels can improve their efficiency, reduce costs, and provide high-quality services to their guests. As the hospitality industry continues to evolve, it is likely that the role and application of organizational communication technologies in hotel management will continue to expand and evolve as well. However, it is important for hotels to carefully consider the benefits and challenges associated with the use of these technologies and to implement them in a way that is user-friendly, secure, and compliant with relevant regulations. Future research could explore the specific types of communication technologies that are most effective in hotel management and the factors that influence their adoption and use.

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